
AN IN-DEPTH ANALYSIS OF JUDICIAL APPOINTMENTS IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

This paper seeks to study the processes of judicial appointments to the higher judiciary in India. The development of conventions and laws starting from the establishment of the Federal Court under the Government of India Act to the situation which prevails today, we have tried to read into the minds of lawmakers, alternatives suggested by members of the Constituent Assembly to various judicial decisions which have moulded the structure to what it is today. Judiciary has the critical task to play in the state, it is the proverbial referee between the people's rights and the general nature of the executive to establish its supremacy. In India, the responsibility lies with the Supreme Court and to a lesser but considerable extent, to the High Courts of the states. It is of interest to understand and study how these courts are composed i.e. how the judges are appointed to these courts. International perspective is sought by studying similar courts established in other countries across the globe and merits and demerits of the present system are tabulated. Finally, the aim is to decide whether the situation warrants any change or not.

I. INTRODUCTION

Roughly speaking, Indians amount for one of every six people living on the planet, and the sheer number makes the study of the Indian public life important. Since India's independence on 15th August, 1947 and subsequent enforcement of our constitution on 26th January, 1950, numerous judicial decisions have shaped and altered lives of what now it the world's most populous nation. Through various judgment by the Supreme Court since its humble beginnings from Chamber of Princes located in the old Parliament, judiciary has amassed a unique influence over the State. This has been made possible by the Constitution's unique mix which provides for Parliamentary Sovereignty mixed with Judicial Supremacy.

By its own judgments, which would form the core debate of this paper, the Supreme Court has evolved a system which essentially makes the judiciary of India very unique. Of all the

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sovereign states which have a comparable model, India is the only country which has a self-appointing judiciary i.e. judges of the Supreme Court appoint their successors. This unique setup raises a few questions as well as answers a few questions of its own, but nevertheless, ever since its establishment, it has been subject to a common debate in the public sphere and has also become the reason for frequent tussles between the executive and legislature coupled against judiciary for power.

Through this paper, the researchers aim to dissect the history, method and impact of judicial appointments. Part II deals with the historical underpinnings of judicial appointments, from pre-independence times until the enforcement of the Constitution. Part III deals with post constitutional developments, including the situation at the enforcement of the constitution and four subsequent cases of the Supreme Court which changed and modified the situation over the years. Part IV includes the International Perspective, where practices of Supreme Courts of comparable nations are discussed. Part V, the crux of the paper, deals with the merits and demerits of the current system. It also includes some numerical data based on the unfulfilled vacancies compared to the sanctioned strengths of the High Courts across the country. Part VI will conclude. Overall, this paper seeks to study the origin of Judicial Appointments, the changes across the years and their impact on the society today.

II. HISTORICAL UNDERPINNINGS

i. Pre-Constitutional History

To understand the collegium system in its current format, it is essential to take a look at its evolution through the course of time. The first High Courts of British India³ were established under the Indian High Courts Act of 1861 and remained the highest courts of appeal within their respective provincial jurisdictions, with an appeal being made possible to the Privy Council. Upon the enactment and subsequent enforcement of the Government of India Act 1935⁴, a Federal Court was established in New Delhi with Sir Maurice Gwyer as the first Chief Justice of India. In all essence, the Federal Court was the predecessor of the current Supreme Court of India.

Chapter I of Part IX of the Act⁵ laid down the foundation of the Federal Court. Section 200(2) talks about the appointment of judges, stating that every judge of the Federal Court shall be appointed by His Majesty by warrant under the Royal Sign Manual. Hence, the Crown enjoyed the power to select Justices and the Chief Justice of the Federal Court. It should also be noted

³ Indian High Courts Act, 1861 (24 & 25 Vict. C. 104)

⁴ Government of India Act 1935 (26 Geo. 5. & 1 Edw. 8. C. 2)

⁵ Ibid.

that under Section 200(3)(c)(ii).⁶ of the Act, the qualifications to become the Chief Justice of India were more stringent than the ordinary judges of the court. The Federal Court first convened on 1st October 1937 in the Chamber of the Princes in the current Parliament building. At this time, the Judges and Chief Justice of the High Courts were also appointed by the Crown in a method similar to that of the Federal Court, as per the relevant provisions of the Act.⁷

ii. Constituent Assembly Debates

Tracing back to the Constituent Assembly Debates, Honorable member Mr. Krishna Chandra Sharma raised Amendment No. 1816⁸ through which he conveyed that the Chief Justice of India should be appointed by the President and for the appointment of other judges of the Supreme Court, the Chief Justice of India must always be consulted.

Via this amendment, Mr. Krishna Chandra Sharma, reasoned that his amendment would carry the same meaning and purpose as the provisions of Section 200 of the Government of India Act, 1935. Under that section, the appointment of Chief Justice of India and other Judges were to be appointed by the King on the advice of his ministers. Under Draft Article 61 of the Constitution, the President has to act on the advice and instance of his Ministers. He further stated the examples of the appointment of Judges in the United States where the Chief Justice of the Supreme Court is appointed by the President. Furthermore, Mr. Sharma stated that the amendment will be in line with the practices in place at other Dominions, along with the Government of India Act as well as what prevailed in the United States at the time.

Also, another Honorable member, Mr. Shibban Lal Saxena proposed amendment No. 1818⁹ which stated that the Chief Justice of India shall be appointed by the President subject to a confirmation by two-thirds majority of Parliament in a joint sitting of both the houses. He wanted the other judges to be appointed by the President on the advice of the Chief Justice of India.

With this amendment, Mr. Saxena wanted the office of The Chief Justice of India to be completely independent of the Executive. Without this provision, he opined that the Chief Justice shall be a creature merely of the executive and the President shall appoint him on the advice of the Prime Minister, which would take away the independence of the Supreme Court. He further argued that the Supreme Court, which is providing for the highest tribunal of justice in our country should be kept above any suspicion and no executive should be able to have any influence upon the court. However, like the previous amendment, this amendment was also not adopted.

⁶ Government of India Act 1935 (26 Geo. 5. & 1 Edw. 8. C. 2), s. 200 (3.) (c.) (ii.)

⁷ Government of India Act 1935 (26 Geo. 5. & 1 Edw. 8. C. 2), s. 220 (2.)

⁸ VIII, Constituent Assembly Debates, 8.90.12 & 8.90.13

⁹ VIII, Constituent Assembly Debates, 8.90.15 & 8.90.16, 24th May 1949

Thirdly, Honorable member B. Pocker moved the amendment No. 1820¹⁰ where he opined that every judge of the Supreme Court of India shall be appointed by the President after consultation and the concurrence of the Chief Justice of India and the Chief Justice of India shall be appointed by the President after consultation with the judges of the Supreme Court and the Chief Justices of the High Courts.

Mr. Pocker believed that the appointment of the judges of the Supreme Court should not be subject to any political influences. He also expressed his support for the opinion of the judges of the Apex Court besides the opinions of the Chief Justices of the various High Courts. Furthermore, he expressed how critical it is for their non-partisan discharge of duties that the Judges of the Supreme Court are not made to feel that their existence or their appointment is dependent upon political patronage or on the will of any political party. He asserted that if a Judge owes his appointment to a political party, he will develop a need to give some consideration for the political views of the authority that has appointed him. It is clear that Mr. Pocker wanted judicial supremacy in judicial appointments.

All of these amendments raised by the Honorable members of the constituent assembly, though not adopted, did play a role in shaping up the constitutional provisions which were finally adopted in the original Constitution enforced on 26th January 1950.

III. POST CONSTITUTIONAL DEVELOPMENTS

Constitutional Provisions as on 26th January 1950

The Constitution of India was fully enforced on 26th January 1950. Article 124(2)¹¹ deals with the appointment of judges of the Supreme Court. Similarly, Article 217¹² deals with the appointment of judges of the High Courts across the country.

Article 124(2) reads as follows:

Every Judge of the Supreme Court shall be appointed by the President by warrant under his hand and seal after consultation with such of the Judges of the Supreme Court and of the High Courts in the States as the President may deem necessary for the purpose and shall hold office until he attains the age of sixty five years: Provided that in the case of appointment of a Judge other than the chief Justice, the chief Justice of India shall always be consulted:

(a) a Judge may, by writing under his hand addressed to the President, resign his office;

(b) a Judge may be removed from his office in the manner provided in clause (4).

¹⁰ VIII, Constituent Assembly Debates, 8.90.18 & 8.90.19, 24th May 1949

¹¹ The Constitution of India, art. 124

¹² The Constitution of India, art. 217

Similarly, Article 217(2) reads:

Every Judge of a High Court shall be appointed by the President by warrant under his hand and seal after consultation with the Chief Justice of India, the Governor of the State, and, in the case of appointment of a Judge other than the chief Justice, the chief Justice of the High court, and shall hold office, in the case of an additional or acting Judge, as provided in Article 224, and in any other case, until he attains the age of sixty two years.

Provided that:

- (a) a Judge may, by writing under his hand addressed to the President, resign his office;*
- (b) a Judge may be removed from his office by the President in the manner provided in clause (4) of Article 124 for the removal of a Judge of the Supreme Court;*
- (c) the office of a Judge shall be vacated by his being appointed by the President to be a Judge of the Supreme Court or by his being transferred by the President to any other High Court within the territory of India.*

From both of the aforementioned provisions which were part of the Constitution as on 26th January 1950, it is evidently clear that judges were appointed by the executive i.e. the President. After the enforcement of the Constitution and the subsequent establishment of the Supreme Court of India, it was the executive who was responsible for the appointment of judges. The term *consultation* used in Articles 124(2) and 217(1) were not construed to be binding upon the executive whilst appointing judges.

First Judges Case: SP Gupta vs. Union of India 1981¹³

The first judges case was the culmination of a series of legal disputes which came to the forefront in regards to the appointment of judges to the Supreme Court. The key battle was between the role of the executive and the judiciary in the appointment of judges.

In its opinion, the Supreme Court held that the primacy in judicial appointments rested with the Chief Justice of India (CJI). However, it also stated that the CJI's recommendation on judicial appointments could be refused by the government for "cogent reasons".

Hence, the case clearly gave supremacy to the Executive over the Judiciary in judicial appointments. This case set the backdrop for the upcoming legal developments and the subsequent cases that shaped the dynamics between the executive and the judiciary in matters of judicial appointments.

Second Judges Case: Supreme Court Advocates-On-Record Assn. vs. Union of India 1993¹⁴

This case partially overruled the judgement of the first judges case. In this case, the Supreme Court revisited the issue of appointment of judges in the higher judiciary. Overruling the

¹³ S.P. Gupta v. Union of India, 1981 Supp SCC 87

¹⁴ Supreme Court Advocates-on-Record Assn. v. Union of India, (1993) 4 SCC 441

executive supremacy it had given to the executive over the judiciary in the First Judges Case, the court ruled in favour of the judiciary this time. Most importantly, this case is of note because it introduced the collegium system for the first time.

The key ruling was that the consultation between the CJI and the President should be more meaningful and effective. The executive was allowed to express their concerns upon the recommendation of names, but ultimately the CJI's recommendation was given more weightage. It was starkly different from what the court had decided in the first judges case.

The court in this case also stated that it was not the CJI's individual opinion, but an institutional opinion formed in consultation with two senior most judges of the Supreme Court. Hence, the collegium as envisaged in this case consisted of the Chief Justice of India along with two senior most judges of the Supreme Court.

Third Judges Case: In Re: Special Reference No. 1 of 1998¹⁵

The third judges case emerged as a result of the power tussle battle between the executive and judiciary to determine their respective roles in the appointment of judges to the higher judiciary. The case was prompted by a Presidential Reference under Article 143.¹⁶

In its opinion, the Supreme Court streamlined the Collegium System even further. The court expanded the collegium to include the Chief Justice and four senior most puisne judges. It also laid down the directive that if two of the judges disagreed with the CJI's opinion, then such opinion could not be recommended. It was also provided that if the CJI disagrees on a person's appointment, then such person shall not be recommended.

As for the appointments and transfers to the High Court, the sole opinion of the CJI was held to be not enough in this case. It was recommended that the opinion of the CJI under articles 217¹⁷ and 222¹⁸ implies consultation with a plurality of judges in the formation of opinion of the CJI. For the appointments of judges to the High Court, the collegium should comprise of the Chief Justice of India and two senior most puisne judges and for the transfer from one High Court to the other, a collegium comprising of the CJI and four senior most puisne judges should take the decision.

Fourth Judges Case: Supreme Court Advocates on Record Ass. vs Union of India 2015¹⁹

The fourth judges case came in the backdrop of the 99th Constitutional Amendment, 2014 and The National Judicial Appointments Commission Act, 2014²⁰ which envisaged a National Judicial Appointments Commission (NJAC). The NJAC was created with the objective to

¹⁵ Special Reference No.1 of 1998, Re, (1998) 7 SCC 739

¹⁶ The Constitution of India, art. 143

¹⁷ The Constitution of India, art. 217

¹⁸ The Constitution of India, art. 222

¹⁹ Supreme Court Advocates-On-Record Ass. v. Union of India, (2015) 6 SCC 408

²⁰ The Constitution (Ninety-Ninth Amendment) Act, 2014 and The National Judicial Appointments Commission Act, 2014 (40 of 2014)

replace the collegium system, which has been the primary organ to appoint judges ever since the third judges case of 1998.

The NJAC was designed to consist of six members, viz. Chief Justice of India, two senior most puisne judges of the Supreme Court, the Union Minister of Law and Justice and two eminent persons to be nominated by a committee consisting of the Prime Minister, the CJI, and the Leader of the Opposition in the Lok Sabha (or the leader of the largest opposition party in the Lok Sabha).

However, in its judgement, the Supreme Court struck down the NJAC laws for violating the Basic Structure of the Constitution and for violating the principle of Judicial Independence.

IV. INTERNATIONAL PERSPECTIVE

Getting an international perspective into judicial appointments will give us a clearer perspective on how the juristic minds of different countries think. For this purpose, we have taken a few nations who have a comparable higher judiciary to India.

In this section we have discussed Israel, South America and United States choose the judges for their Supreme Court.

i. Israel

In Israel, the Judicial Selection Committee is the body that appoints judges to Israeli Courts. Established in 1953, after the enactment of the Judges Bill, it was intended to prevent outside political pressure and to ensure the independence of the judiciary. As per the Basic Law: the Judiciary, 1984, the committee consists of nine members, viz.

- Justice Minister – Chairman
- A Cabinet Minister, selected by the Cabinet
- Two Knesset Members (Israeli Parliament). Since 1992, they usually appoint one member from the ruling side and the other from the opposition.
- Two Members from the Bar Association. Usually, members are selected from two of the largest factions in the bureau.
- The President of the Supreme Court
- Two Judges of the Supreme Court other than the President of the Supreme Court

The President of the Supreme Court, equivalent to the Chief Justice of India, is a selection based on the seniority of judges in the court, a practice which is also followed in India.

Overall, the method of judicial appointments in Israel follow a balanced approach where members from executive, legislature and judiciary are consulted along with a non-state actor i.e. the Israeli Bar Association. This creates checks and balances between the three organs of

the state while also including outside participation to some extent.

ii. South Africa

The Judicial Service Commission is a body constituted by the South African Constitution²¹ to make recommendations for the appointment to the Judiciary of South Africa. The Commission is composed of 23 members, including political as well as non-political posts. The members are mentioned in section 178 (1.) (a.) – (k.) of the Constitution.

The system followed in South Africa ensures constitutional independence as the procedure and composition is clearly prescribed in the constitution. It also ensures judicial diversity, participation of various stakeholders as well as taking into account public inputs and maintaining transparency.

iii. United States of America

In the United States, the Supreme Court judges are selected by a process which originates as a nomination by the President. Then, the Judiciary Committee of the Senate reviews the nomination of the prescribed candidate. The committee can hold confirmation hearings where senators could question the potential candidate. After that, the judiciary committee votes whether to recommend the nominated candidate for a full senate vote. This vote, while influential, is not binding. Then, the nomination is put to a full senate vote, where a simple majority confirms their nomination and they are subsequently appointed to the US Supreme Court.

Compared to the system of appointments in India, Israel and South Africa, the United States' way of appointments warrants a lot of power to the executive and legislature. There is a good chance of political patronage if the senate is controlled by the same party from which the President comes from.

V. MERITS AND DE-MERITS OF THE COLLEGIUM

From the previous section, it is evident that the methods of judicial appointments across the sample of countries we have studied are considerably different from each other. However, all of the aforementioned nations, including India, have had a potent judiciary in their own accord over the years. For an in-depth analysis of where the Indian system of appointments via the collegium fares well and where it does not, we will be outlining merits and de-merits of the collegium system.

²¹ The Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996 (108 of 1996) s. 178 (1.) (a.)-(k.)

Merits

a. Independence of the Judiciary

The collegium system of judicial appointments ensures the independence of judiciary from the executive and legislative branches of the government. The appointment process of both Chief Justice of the Supreme Court as well as the Chief Justices of the High Courts, along with puisne judges of the Supreme Court and the High Courts is not dependent upon any confirmation or acceptance of the Executive or the Legislature. This ensures that once a person is appointed as judge in any of the higher courts i.e. the Supreme Court or the High Courts, they do not get to the position due to any political patronage or personal preferences of the Executive. This is essential to ensure non-partisan behavior of judges, especially when the Government itself is subject to many suits in the courts.

b. Expertise and experience-based appointments

The collegium system allows sitting judges, who themselves have been part of the legal sphere for a major parts of their lives, to choose the next judges of the court. This can lead to appointment of persons with great legal acumen and expertise to the bench. The judges spend a lot of time with an array legal practitioners while in court, both from the bar and the bench. Also, since the judges are experts in the legal field, they are qualified to judge the legal acumen of potential candidates as well as draw from their personal experiences with a lot of them.

c. Institutional Memory

Given the fact that only the senior most judges constitute the collegium, it is likely that the members of the collegium will have a great understanding about the institution i.e. the Supreme Court or in case of High Court judges, the High Court. This would allow the collegium to recommend better fits to the bench and people who could maintain continuity and preserve the institutional memory of the judiciary would be selected. This is of significant importance, because judges will come and go, but the courts as institutions will continue long before judges have retired.

d. Accountability of Judges remains with the Judges

Since the collegium ensures that judiciary is self-appointing in nature, the judges who get promoted through elevation from lower courts would be held accountable to the judges of the collegium of their High Court and to the Supreme Court collegium. The scrutiny as well as the appraisal of the performances of the judges who could potentially be elevated is done by the members of the collegium, leaving room for no executive interference in the matter.

Demerits

a. Lack of Accountability and Transparency

Perhaps the most vocal criticism of the Collegium has been the lack of accountability and transparency. In the previous sections, we have discussed how judges are appointed to the apex courts of Israel, South Africa and the United States. All of them, have some degree of involvement of other organs of the state i.e. Executive and Judiciary. In India, the President is the only authority over judicial appointments, and her role is merely ceremonial in nature. It leaves the members of the collegium having no real accountability to the people or other state institutions at large.

On the other hand, the lack of transparency of the collegium has also been a common target for the detractors of the system. This is not without reason because despite of the reassurances from the members of the collegium about increasing the transparency about what happens in its meetings, the stakeholders get limited insights into the criteria used for selecting or rejecting candidates. It has often led to cries of nepotism and favouritism as reasons for selection and non-selection are not made clear. All in all, the criteria for consideration and subsequent selection or non-selection of a candidate remains opaque to the public and other stakeholders.

b. Limited Representation

The collegium confines the process of judicial appointments to only the sitting judges and while there is an advantage which can be construed from the vast judicial and legal experience of the judges, there is a larger picture of lack of representation of different legal and professional backgrounds. This is mostly seen in the processes of Israel and South Africa. In Israel, the members of the bar associations are involved in the appointment process whereas in South Africa, the committee includes advocates, attorneys as well as teachers of law, making the committee potentially diverse.

The monochromatic composition of collegium has resulted in under-representation of various communities at the higher courts. Most notably, the Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribe communities are numerically underrepresented. There is an equally dull figure, if not worse, in terms of gender diversity. There have been very few female judges at the Supreme Court level, and no female judge has ever become the Chief Justice of India. Since independence, we have had women occupying various important public offices, including but not limited to, the President, Prime Minister and the Speaker of Lok Sabha. However, it is encouraging that we will, in all likelihood, have a female Chief Justice very soon.

c. Judicial Elitism

The collegium has also been accused to promote judicial elitism, where sitting judges have a significant influence over their own appointments and promotions, potentially leading to a closed and exclusive system. Former Supreme Court judge and the sole dissenter in the case which struck down NJAC, Justice Jasti Chelameshwar quoted former Supreme Court judge Justice Ruma Pal that the collegium acted like a coterie, and that there was a barter system among the member judges during the infamous four judges press conference in 2018.²²

d. Delay in Appointments and subsequent unfulfilled vacancies

Collegiums of both the High Courts as well as the Supreme Court comprise of the Chief Justices of the respective courts along with the senior most judges. The amount of time spent in deliberating, discussing and studying the possible candidature of prospects to be appointed to the bench is a time consuming process. The Chief Justices, who are also *masters of the roster* i.e. allocate and constitute benches for cases in their respective courts have another responsibility which leaves them with even less time. It should be understood that the judges of the collegium, like all other judges of the court are equally responsible to listen to cases and dispense justice, which is the primary job of judiciary.

Coupled with this are disagreements among members of the collegium, non-acceptance of the tendered names from the High Court collegium to the Supreme Court, and the unlimited streams of cases which daily make their way to the courts. It leaves less time of the collegium to hold meetings while sometimes due to lack of consensus, the candidates are not selected or elevated. All these delays in appointments have led to a very gruesome situation of unfulfilled vacancies. As of 1st August 2023, only 778 positions out of 1114 have been filled across various High Courts. If the context of the overburdening of cases in the High Courts is taken into view, it paints a bleak picture.

VI. CONCLUSION

The culmination of all the facts and opinions stated in this paper about the collegium system reveals a complex tapestry of its merits and shortcomings, with threads woven through landmark judgments that have not only conceived it but also thrown light to its shortcomings. As we conclude this exploration, it is clear that the collegium's journey has been marked by its pivotal stance against any possible executive dominance, the public-centric verdicts of the Supreme Court over the years, but also of its gaps in terms of accountability,

²² Dhananjay Mahapatra, Supreme Court Row: Seniority is a sacred principle for judges, The Times of India, 13th January 2018, available at <<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/supreme-court-row-seniority-is-a-sacred-principle-for-judges/articleshow/62481242.cms>> (last visited on 18th August 2023)

underrepresentation of communities as well as women. All of this has raised essential questions which raise a series of questions.

In the annals of Indian jurisprudence, the collegium emerged as a bastion against the excesses of the executive, and combined with other landmark judicial decisions over the years, has firmly propelled the Supreme Court of India to a position where perhaps it is fair to say that it is the strongest Supreme Court in the world.

The Supreme Court of India has used its powers with great aplomb, visible through a series of its judgements over the years. It has safeguarded the sanctity of the constitution and provided justice to the people who most needed it. A lot of it had been made possible due to the independence the court enjoys, and the independence of the higher judiciary in terms of appointments of judges, is an integral part of such independence.

However, this positive outlook of the higher judiciary is incomplete. The lack of transparency and accountability on part of members of the collegium imposes a question mark on the system. Above all, India is a democratic nation, and transparency and accountability are the bedrock of a democratic civilization. The collegium cannot be a tool which uses the guise of independence of judiciary to hold secretive processes with a veil of uncertainty. The opacity surrounding the whole appointment process and its subsequent results have given rise to concerns ranging from favouritism, nepotism and even political biases of the members.

Justice delivery is the heart and soul of any judicial system. If justice is delayed for any reason, or the courts are unable to take cases due to lack of judges, it is a gargantuan failure, especially the systems and the people in place to fulfil the vacancies. In India, justice delivery has a double problem. There are considerable amounts of unfulfilled vacancies in the High Courts of the country, and to add fuel to fire, every day, countless cases make their way to be listed in these courts. The collegium has the power to recommend and appoint judges, but its lack of ability to address this issue is well documented. It is only natural that questions will be raised to ensure timely and effective administration of justice, which is the cornerstone of a functional legal framework.

Moreover, the stark underrepresentation in the composition of judges, both past and present is alarming. Lack of diversity, particularly in terms of caste, gender and legal background have put the system to a test, often by executives i.e. the ministers in the government, but also at times by public at large, and to a rarer extent, sometimes sitting judges of the Supreme Court.

Across all sectors of human pursuit not only in India but across the world, major strides have been taken in the last decade, but there is an absence of concrete affirmative action for people with historically disadvantaged backgrounds. There is a clear disparity on lines of caste, gender and family background, where first generation legal practitioners and practitioners who do not

have familial or friendly relations with people who have had a look-in inside the collegium, are at a disadvantage to people who have had the fortune of knowing or befriending members of the collegium. The current collegium might have successfully evaded executive interference, but this closed body might just lead to familial patronage, where certain families might end up benefiting each other. Multiple members of the same family have managed to become judges as well as Chief Justice of the Supreme Court before a woman has had a chance to become the Chief Justice.

These disparities underscore the need for introspection and reform to ensure that the composition of the judges of the country's higher courts is worthy of the nation's widely celebrated pluralistic character.

In conclusion, the collegium stands as a paradox of promise and perplexity. It has shown great resilience against executive intrusions and even rendered verdicts that reverberate public-centric ethos. Yet, its opacity, inefficiency, questions on meritocracy of selections and acute underrepresentation of communities and classes of people paint a canvas of imbalance.

As India evolves into a modern nation with no scope for age-old malpractices of caste discrimination, nepotism and patriarchy, its institutions, which include the judiciary, should adhere to the modernness of the state. Reforms are needed, and they should be implemented, preferably from within, as our learned judges have time and again applied from the bench while writing judgements enshrining modern ethos. The invention of the collegium is a testament to India's relentless pursuit of justice and equity, a journey which has intermingled our past, present and future. However, the current shape of the system is not in consonance of where the nation is headed. The members of the collegium should be made accountable and the process itself should be made codified. Judiciary has to be independent, but it has to be independent of the executive. For all its might, it is not independent of the law or even, the people it has jurisdiction over.

As the famous political activist Thomas Paine once said –

“A body of men holding themselves accountable to nobody ought not be trusted by anybody”

The reforms must adhere to Mr. Paine's logic, and the iron curtain of opacity in matters of judicial appointments must be lifted.
